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DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF HYBRID CARBON FIBER LAMINATE BEAM UNDER BALLISTIC IMPACT

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Background

- The total annual economic losses induced by bird strikes in the global aviation industry is between **\$64-\$107** million , around **13%** of all occurring at the aircraft engines.

Can we improve ballistic impact performance by changing the stiffness of matrix for fibre reinforced laminates ?

Fibre reinforcement

- Pyrofil TR50S 15K carbon fibres (diameter is $7\ \mu\text{m}$)

Epoxy resin matrix

- EF80 flexible epoxy resin for *flexible* laminates
- IN2 epoxy infusion resin for *stiff* laminates

Supplier - Easy Composites Ltd, UK

RTM manufacturing process

(a)

0.1 mm single unidirectional carbon fibre layer

(b)

Nomex honeycomb core sandwich beam

Hybrid laminate beam

Quasi-static stress-strain relationships of the stiff and soft fibre composites under uniaxial compression and tension tests for (a) 0° /90° and (b) ±45° lay-up architecture.

Quasi-static out-of-plane compressive response of the Nomex honeycomb core of density

Sketch of the experimental setup for ballistic impact

Details of the monolithic and sandwich beams

Composite sheets	Monolithic beams			Sandwich beams		
	Stiff	Soft	Hybrid	Stiff face sheet	Soft face sheet	Hybrid face sheet
Sketch of beams						
Number of layers for sheet	20	20	10*2	8*2	8*2	4*4
Areal density of face sheets (kg/m ²)	5.38	5.38	5.30	4.30	4.30	4.30
Areal mass of honeycomb core(kg/m ²)	0	0	0	0.54	0.54	0.54
Areal mass of glue (kg/m ²)	0	0	0.14	0.28	0.28	0.56
Total areal mass of beams (kg/m ²)	5.38	5.38	5.44	5.12	5.12	5.40

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Results and Discussion

Impact responses of stiff monolithic beams

- **Rebound** $v_0 \leq 61.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$
- **Three-point fracture** $61.5 \text{ ms}^{-1} < v_0 \leq 116.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$
- **Perforation** $v_0 > 116.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$

Stiff monolithic beams

Impact responses of soft monolithic beams

- **Rebound**

$$v_0 \leq 84 \text{ ms}^{-1}$$

- **One-point fracture**

$$84 \text{ ms}^{-1} < v_0 \leq 232.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$$

- **Perforation**

$$v_0 > 232.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$$

Soft monolithic beams

Impact responses of hybrid monolithic beams

- **Rebound** $v_0 \leq 86 \text{ ms}^{-1}$
- **Three-point fracture**
 $86 \text{ ms}^{-1} < v_0 \leq 235 \text{ ms}^{-1}$
- **Perforation**
 $v_0 \geq 235 \text{ ms}^{-1}$

Hybrid monolithic beams

Comparison

The critical velocities regarding to the different damage modes of stiff, soft and hybrid monolithic beams

Impact responses of sandwich beams

Comparison of initial – residual velocity

Initial projectile velocity &
Residual projectile velocity

Comparison of energy transmitted to beams

Kinetic energy of the projectile transmitted to the beams as a function of initial kinetic energy of the projectile.

- The **hybrid** and **soft** monolithic beam had similar critical velocities for each failure mode, and both higher than the **stiff** monolithic beam.
- The **hybrid** monolithic beam had benefits under low velocity impact as the failure only occurred in the stiff composite part of beam and the soft part could still resisting loading.
- The **soft** and **hybrid** monolithic beams have better energy absorption capacity compared to stiff monolithic beams and sandwich beams.
- For the sandwich beams, the **hybrid-face sandwich beams** exhibited better energy absorption capacity than the soft-face sandwich beams at high impact velocity.
- The **weak adhesive** interface between the stiff and soft composite parts in hybrid monolithic/sandwich beams may have a positive effect on the energy absorption capacity of beams.